
Modality in President Joko Widodo's State Speech: A Corpus-Based Discourse Analysis

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine whether President Joko Widodo's speech in 2021 reflects the same damaging and gloomy mindset as Joko Widodo's speech in 2020, as researched by Surahmat (2020). This study employs a descriptive qualitative approach based on Alwi's (1992) modality theoretical approach, with the data being President Joko Widodo's state speech presented during the MPR/DPR plenary session 2021. The data was collected and processed using the AntConc corpus tool to change the document format for processing lexical data. The data analysis method is a quantitative data descriptive analysis approach based on the occurrence of the lexicon as the keyword with high frequency and concordance so that other grammatical markers (modalities) are recognized to generate meaning in the conversation. Furthermore, to support the claim, the study depicts the context of the event at which President Joko Widodo delivered his address. The results demonstrate that the keywords that emerge consistently are 'HARUS' as an epistemic modality marker and 'BISA' as a dynamic modality marker containing the notion of capacity. The requirement and habit demonstrated by the government through President Jokowi's state speech illustrate the government and his optimistic approach toward coronavirus prevention, even though positive COVID-19 cases increased during the state speech's delivery.

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1. Introduction

Halliday and Matthiessen (2014) stated that language has three fundamental roles for expressing information: ideational functions, interpersonal functions, and textual functions, all referred to as meta-functional functions that suggest various realities. The ideational function is used to expose physical-biological truth, the interpersonal function is used to show social reality, and the textual function is used to reveal semiotic reality or the reality of symbols. These three language metafunctions refer to three types of meaning: ideational, interpersonal, and textual (Adenan, 2000). This study will concentrate on interpersonal functions and meanings since they concern the interaction between speakers and listeners in spoken or writer-reader interactions in written language.

Language and discourse are inextricably linked. Discourse is a critical component of language development. Kridalaksana (2013) stated that discourse is the whole language unit and the highest or largest grammatical unit in the grammatical hierarchy. Discourse cannot be separated from context because it is a complete language unit. According to Halliday (in Adenan, 2000), two factors influence language use: the situational context and the cultural context. The context alluded to in this work is the situational context. The components of the situation's context are field, tenor, and mode. Interpersonal functions in discourse have meanings formed due to the realization of grammatical features that consider language as an act or means of acting, which is called interpersonal meaning (Halliday and Hassan, 1992).

The tone of discourse is one of the components utilized to support the context of the situation in discourse and serves to develop and maintain social ties as the realization of the social role in communication created by language (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2014). Khaofia (2018) also stated that the vertical and horizontal dimensions of interpersonal connections are the essential determinants of tenor (involvement) It requires a linguistic characteristic, modality, to show interpersonal relationships vertically and horizontally. In interpersonal communication, Kridalaksana (2013) defines modality as how the speaker displays his perspective toward the circumstance. According to Chaer (2002), this speaker's method is a statement in a sentence expressing the speaker's attitude toward the subject under discussion. This speaker's attitude will be discussed in President Joko Widodo's state speech at the MPR/DPR plenary session in 2021, which was influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic conditions.

The COVID-19 pandemic has spread globally, including Indonesia. On March 2, 2020, two people in Indonesia were verified to have contracted COVID-19 from a Japanese citizen (Jaya, 2021; Susilo, 2020). The pandemic expanded to all provinces, with DKI Jakarta, West Java, and Central Java being the most affected (Jaya, 2021). As of March 31, 2020, data reveal 1,528 confirmed cases and 136 deaths. Since then, the Indonesian government has declared COVID-19 a public health emergency that must be addressed under Presidential Decree No. 11 of 2020 concerning the Determination of the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Public Health Emergency (Syauqi, 2020). The government implemented various measures and procedures to disrupt the transmission of this virus. They started with socialization efforts, drafting legislation as the legal foundation for prosecution. Even though the pandemic influenced the economy, the government implemented numerous policies to rescue the people's economy and maintain economic stability on a micro and macro scale (Syauqi, 2020). Various policies and initiatives are still being monitored and communicated to the public through various media discourses, from mass media to state information media, given by COVID-19 task force spokespersons, ministry officials, and the president himself.

The research on modalities has previously been undertaken by Faradi (2015), Prihantoro & Fitriani (2015), Harahap (2017), Charmilasari (2018), Khaofia (2018), Puspito (2018), Ayuningtyas (2021), and Risaldi et al. (2021). Faradi (2015) examines modalities in online news texts using data collected via the LSE web corp corpus tool and analyzed using Fairclough's critical discourse analysis technique. In online news writings, researchers discovered several modalities: intentional, epistemic,

deontic, dynamic, and modal—athleticism. Prihantoro & Fitriani (2015) use Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) theory to describe the messages of values behind the dominant frequency in modalities realized with the ideological context, cultural context, and situational context in the text of the debate between the candidates for the presidential and vice-presidential elections of the Republic of Indonesia in 2014-2019.

Harahap (2017) examines modalities' types, values, and orientations in President Joko Widodo's speeches at several international conferences in 2014. According to the findings, President Joko Widodo employs probability modalization with medium and low values. At intermediate values, there is tendency modulation and subjective-explicit modality orientation. Charmilasari (2018) uses Halliday's theory of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) to define the modality utilized by teachers in framing learning in the classroom. As a result, the probability modality dominates at intermediate levels since teachers' transmission of information and knowledge is still viewed as uncertain. Using systemic functional linguistics (SFL), Khaofia (2018) analyzes and explains the relationship of modality to interpersonal meaning in Mata Najwa on Stage "All Because of Ahok." It suggests that Najwa Shihab's relationship with the informants is unequal.

Puspito (2018) used modality and transitivity techniques in reporting on the 2017 DKI Jakarta Pilkada in Kompas newspaper using a critical discourse analysis approach, concluding that Kompas newspaper is pro-Indonesian values. Ayuningtyas (2021) examines the modalities utilized by US President Joe Biden in his speech to commemorate regional closures at the start of the COVID-19 epidemic. Her findings reveal three modalities in his speech: tendencies, possibilities, and obligations. Biden's self-images include visionary, bold, melancholy, robust, and respectful. Through online netnographic observations of pedophile community participants, Risaldi et al. (2021) demonstrated the modalities of practicing criminal power in the pedophile community. According to the findings of his study, there is a modality as a linguistic component of power practice that contains (1) the relational value of the modality, which is signaled by the modal *may*, *will*, and *could*, and (2) the expressive value of the modality, which is represented by the modal *must*.

It can be concluded that Prihantoro & Fitriani (2015), Harahap (2017), Charmilasari (2018), Khaofia (2018), and Ayuningtyas (2021) used Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics approach in examining modalities, whereas Faradi (2015), Harahap's (2017), Puspito (2018), and Risaldi, et al. (2021) used a critical discourse analysis approach. In contrast to the previous research that has been mentioned, this study employs only text analysis to investigate the dominance of modalities via corpus data processing with the AntCont as corpus data processing tool. Therefore, this research question is how to determine the type of modality based on Alwi's (1992) theory in President Jokowi's state speech presented at the MPR/DPR Session in 2021.

2. Materials and Methods

This study employs a descriptive qualitative methodological approach based on modalities as a theoretical approach. The terms used in this study serve as modality markers in President Joko Widodo's state speech. The information was obtained from the official website of the Republic of Indonesia Cabinet Secretariat, which provides the full text of President Joko Widodo's state speech at the MPR/DPR plenary session in 2021 (the Republic of Indonesia Cabinet Secretariat, 2021). President Joko Widodo's whole state speech has been converted into an MS Word document. The MS Word document was then transformed into a PDF document, which was translated back into txt format. This study used AntConc software version 3.5.8 to change the document format for processing lexical data (Anthony, 2019). The software can segment text into words (lexicon), order words with high frequency, and display word collocations and concordance. This study's high-frequency terms or lexicon will be treated as keywords. The keywords to seek are words that serve as modality markers and are then searched for concordance to define the meaning produced in President Jokowi's state speech.

The data analysis method employed is a descriptive analysis of quantitative data based on the appearance of the lexicon, which serves as a high-frequency marker of modality (the lexicon being the keyword) and concordance, which explains the meaning generated in the discourse. In addition, the analysis illustrates the context of the situation when discourse is presented to reinforce the argument. High-frequency keywords will quantitatively support the qualitative analysis of President Joko Widodo's state speech. According to Fairclough (2003), detecting keywords in a text corpus against co-occurrence patterns or collocations between keywords and other words can demonstrate how quantitative analysis is applicable and boost qualitative analysis. After finding concordance from each high-frequency term, the analysis proceeded using the descriptive analysis method on quantitative data to characterize the meaning constructed using modality markers built into the discourse. In this study, the term modality refers to Alwi's (1992) modality theoretical approach, categorizing modalities in Indonesian into four types: intentional, epistemic, deontic, and dynamic.

3. Results and Discussions

President Joko Widodo's state speech discourse has a corpus size of 872-word types and 2463-word tokens. Table 1 displays the frequency of occurrence of modality marker keywords based on the total size of word types and word tokens.

Table 1. Frequency of Appearance of Modality Markers

No	Modality	Modality Markers	Frequency	Total
1	Intensional	<i>Ingin</i>	2	4
		<i>Mari</i>	1	
		<i>Semoga</i>	1	
2	Epistemik	<i>Harus</i>	18	22
		<i>Mungkin</i>	3	
		<i>Perlu</i>	1	
3	Deontik	<i>Bisa</i>	5	6
		<i>Boleh</i>	1	
		<i>Bisa</i>	11	
4	Dinamik	<i>Dapat</i>	1	16
		<i>Mampu</i>	4	
		Total	48	

Table 1 reveals that the keyword 'HARUS' appears only 22 times as a marker of epistemic modality compared to other keywords. The frequency of recurrence of the keyword at least once was obtained for the words 'BOLEH' as a deontic modality marker, 'DAPAT' as a dynamic modality marker, 'PERLU' as an epistemic modality marker, and 'SEMOGA' as an intentional modality marker. Table 1 further demonstrates that the keyword 'BISA' can represent both deontic and dynamic modes. It follows Alwi's (1992) assertion that the word 'BISA,' in addition to expressing 'ability,' can also express 'permission' and 'possibility.' However, the dynamic modality markers 'BISA' and 'DAPAT,' which contain the ability, can be used interchangeably as adverbs. Furthermore, Table 1 indicates the frequency of the keyword 'BISA,' which is 16 times greater than the frequency of the 'DAPAT,' which is one time. It is because, when used as an adverb, Indonesian speakers are accustomed to using the word 'BISA' to express ability, whereas the word 'DAPAT' is more commonly used as a verb, which means 1) to receive, to acquire (as a form of conversation); 2) found, caught, and so on; and 3) successful, achieved (Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa, 2016).

The context of the relevant situation at the time the discourse was broadcast was supplied before offering a concordance analysis of President Joko Widodo's state speech. President Joko Widodo

delivered his state speech at the Annual Session of the MPR RI and the Joint Session of the DPD RI and the DPR RI on the occasion of the Republic of Indonesia's 76th Anniversary of Independence on August 16, 2021. The setting of crisis that occurred in August 2021 was a new instance of Covid-19 in Indonesia, which escalated to 20 thousand per day on the 76th Independence Day of the Republic of Indonesia, Tuesday, August 17, 2021 (Pratama, 2021). According to Ministry of Health data, new cases surged by 20,741 people in a day, compared to 17,384 instances the day before. As indicated in Figure 1, the overall number of Covid-19 cases in Indonesia during the pandemic was 3.892 million.

Figure 1 Infographics of COVID-19 cases in Indonesia before the Independence Day of the Republic of Indonesia (Source: Pratama, 2021)

Intentional Modality Marker Concordance

The results of the concordance sorting of these keywords can be shown in Table 2 based on the frequency of the intended modality marker keywords as much as 11 times, as stated in Table 1.

Table 2. Concordance of Intentional Modality Marker Keywords

No	Word/Phrase on the Left	Keyword	Word/Phrase on the Right
1	<i>tetapi sekaligus juga bisa menguatkan. Kita</i>	<i>ingin</i>	<i>pandemi ini menerangi kita untuk mawas</i>
2	<i>semakin memperkuat modal sosial kita. Jika</i>	<i>ingin</i>	<i>sehat, warga yang lain juga harus</i>
3	<i>berat ini bisa lebih mudah diselesaikan.</i>	<i>Mari</i>	<i>kita pegang teguh nilai-nilai toleransi,</i>
4	<i>tumbuh dalam menggapai cita-cita bangsa.</i>	<i>Semoga</i>	<i>Allah SWT., Tuhan Yang Mahakuasa, senantiasa</i>

Table 2 demonstrates the use of deliberate modality indicators in data (1) and (2), invitation in data (3), and expectations in data (4). In data (1) and (2), the modality marker 'INGIN' expresses President Joko Widodo's wish for the Indonesian people to be introspective and healthy. Similarly, the modality marker 'MARI' in data (3) conveys an invitation from President Joko Widodo to hold firm to tolerance ideals in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. Finally, in data (4), the modality marker 'SEMOGA' carries President Joko Widodo's prayer and hope to God Almighty that the Indonesian people will try to combat the COVID-19 pandemic. The marker of intentional modality in President Joko Widodo's speech discourse incorporates the invitation, hope, and desire of President Joko Widodo to protect and preserve the Indonesian people from the COVID-19 pandemic. President Jokowi's official speech demonstrates the government and his optimistic stance toward coronavirus prevention.

Epistemic Modality Marker Concordance

The results of the concordance sorting of these keywords may be shown in Table 3 based on the frequency of 22 times the epistemic modality marker term, as stated in Table 1.

Table 3. Concordance of Epistemic Modality Marker Keywords

No	Word/Phrase on the Left	Keyword	Word/Phrase on the Right
1	<i>ingin sehat, warga yang lain juga</i>	<i>harus</i>	<i>sehat. Jika ada seseorang yang tertular</i>
2	<i>semakin responsif. Kita tahu bahwa pandemi</i>	<i>harus</i>	<i>ditangani secara cepat dan terkonsolidasi,</i>
3	<i>akuntabilitas, dan tata kelola yang baik</i>	<i>harus</i>	<i>dijunjung tinggi. Kerja sama antarlembaga,</i>
4	<i>kesehatan masih menjadi kelemahan serius yang</i>	<i>harus</i>	<i>kita pecahkan. Tetapi, pandemi telah memper</i>
5	<i>Dalam mengambil keputusan, pemerintah</i>	<i>harus</i>	<i>terus merujuk kepada data, serta kepada</i>
6	<i>dengan merujuk kepada data-data terkini.</i>	<i>Mungkin</i>	<i>hal ini sering dibaca sebagai kebijakan</i>
7	<i>hukum Pokok-pokok Haluan Negara juga</i>	<i>perlu</i>	<i>diapresiasi untuk melandasi pembangunan Ind</i>

Table 3 illustrates that the application of epistemic modality markers requires data (1), data (5), and data (7), with the possibility of data (6). The modality marker 'HARUS' in data (1) through data (5) represents President Joko Widodo's essential stance toward responding to the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. President Joko Widodo demonstrated this mindset by expressing the government's attempts to deal with COVID-19. Similarly, the modality marker 'PERLU' in data (7) reflects President Joko Widodo's attitude toward the MPR RI members' performance in reviewing the substance and legal form of the Principal Principles of State Policy, which should and should be appreciated for the sake of Indonesia's development. The modality marker 'MUNGKIN' in data (6), on the other hand, contains President Joko Widodo's response to the public's impression of the government's ever-changing policies constricting and easing public mobility during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. If the context is unclear, it will appear unconfident. The marker of epistemic modality in President Joko Widodo's state speech incorporates the government's necessity and possibility in making decisions and policies to not confuse the public in carrying out operations during the COVID-19 pandemic. President Jokowi's state speech demonstrates the government and his optimism regarding coronavirus prevention.

Deontic Modality Marker Concordance

The results of the concordance sorting of these keywords may be shown in Table 4 based on the frequency of deontic modality marker keywords six times, as stated in Table 1.

Table 4. Concordance of Deontic Modality Marker Keywords

No	Word/Phrase on the Left	Keyword	Word/Phrase on the Right
1	<i>dan pandemi itu seperti api. Kalau</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>kita hindari, tetapi, jika hal itu</i>

2	<i>yang dihadapi. Pengetatan mobilitas yang tidak</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>dihindari ini membuat pemerintah harus member</i>
3	<i>pandemi bukan situasi normal, dan tidak</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>diperiksa dengan standar situasi normal. Yang</i>
4	<i>kerja dalam pelayanan peradilan juga tidak</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>ditunda, bahkan harus dipercepat. Proses adm</i>
5	<i>saling membantu. Tidak ada orang yang</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>aman dari ancaman COVID-19, selama masih</i>
6	<i>laju pertumbuhan ekonomi, tetapi pandemi tidak</i>	<i>boleh</i>	<i>menghambat proses reformasi struktural pere</i>

Table 4 demonstrates that the employment of deontic modality markers encompasses possibilities in data (1) through data (5), as well as a requirement in data (6). The modality marker 'BISA' in data (1) to (5) has a different conceivable interpretation from the modality marker 'MUNGKIN' in Table 3 data (6). The modality marker 'MUNGKIN' contains the possibility of an occurrence of a fact or phenomenon. However, the modality marker 'BISA' in data (1) to (5) contains the possibility if the word 'KALAU' is followed by the negative form 'TIDAK' to 'TIDAK BISA' as in data (2) to data (4), or the phrase nothing can be like data (5).

The form of negation 'TIDAK' connected before the modality marker 'BISA' contains no opposing subtleties that imply a gloomy attitude from the administration. However, the attitude displayed is optimistic that the COVID-19 pandemic is unavoidable; hence coronavirus prevention must be handled with "abnormal" standards. The launch of the COVID-19 immunization campaign will begin in January 2021, or seven months before President Joko Widodo's state speech (Direktorat Jenderal Pencegahan dan Pengendalian Penyakit, 2021).

Furthermore, the word 'BISA' in data (2) to data (4) can be replaced with the phrase 'DAPAT'; however, data (1) and data (5) cannot be replaced with the word 'DAPAT.' It is because data (1) is followed by the term 'KALAU,' which implies the probability of an occurrence. Similarly, in data (5), the word "tidak ada yang bisa" is followed by the adjective aman; hence the phrase "tidak ada yang bisa aman" can be understood as "tidak ada yang mungkin aman."

In addition, the imperative meaning of the modality marker 'BOLEH' in data (6) differs from that of the modality marker 'HARUS' in Table 3 of data (1) to data 5. The modality marker HARUS is more necessary than the modality marker BOLEH. It is because the term 'BOLEH' means "permission or approval." When the word 'BOLEH' is followed by the negation form 'TIDAK' to produce 'TIDAK BOLEH,' the word 'BOLEH' takes on the sense of a ban.

The deontic modality marker in President Joko Widodo's state address contains the impossibility of unavoidable things (data 2), cannot be checked (data 3), and cannot be postponed (data 4) regarding several possible things that may occur during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. Similarly, deontic modality markers must be used to negate 'TIDAK BOLEH' to the COVID-19 pandemic, which must not impede the structural reform process in dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic. President Jokowi's official speech demonstrates the government and his optimistic stance toward coronavirus prevention.

Dynamic Modality Marker Concordance

The results of the concordance sorting of these keywords can be shown in Table 5 based on the frequency of dynamic modality marker keywords 16 times, as given in Table 1.

No	Word/Phrase on the Left	Keyword	Word/Phrase on the Right
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1	<i>di era Revolusi Industri 4.0 ini, agar</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>bekerja lebih efektif, lebih efisien, dan</i>
2	<i>menjadi salah satu kunci utama untuk</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>gesit merespons perubahan yang terjadi di</i>
3	<i>upsi. Indonesia Tangguh, Indonesia Tumbuh, hanya</i>	<i>bisa</i>	<i>dicapai jika kita semua bahu-membahu</i>
4	<i>rantai pasok global. Hal ini diharapkan</i>	<i>dapat</i>	<i>meningkatkan daya saing produk UMKM, serta</i>
5	<i>tahan banting, yang kokoh, dan yang</i>	<i>mampu</i>	<i>memenangkan gelombang pertandingan. Perjal</i>
6	<i>sektor kesehatan meningkat pesat dan semakin</i>	<i>mampu</i>	<i>menghadapi ketidakpastian yang tinggi dalam</i>

Table 5 illustrates that dynamic modality markers have capabilities, such as in data (1) to data (6). Data (1) to data (6) comprise abilities since they are followed by numerous verbs, including work (data 1), answer (data 2), achieve (data 3), improve (data 4), win (data 5), and face (data 6). Even the modal markers 'BISA,' 'DAPAT,' and 'MAMPU' can be used interchangeably. It can be deduced that the markers of dynamic modalities in President Joko Widodo's state speech comprise the capacities the government wishes to attain to deal with the many changes caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. It is accomplished by working more effectively, adjusting to changes, collaborating, boosting competitiveness, winning waves of competition, and dealing with uncertainty. President Jokowi's official speech demonstrates the government and his hopeful stance toward COVID-19 prevention.

4. Conclusion

The keywords that regularly arise in President Joko Widodo's state speech discourse are 'HARUS' as a marker of epistemic modality and 'BISA' as a marker of dynamic modality, which contains the notion of ability. The necessity and habit demonstrated by the Indonesian government through President Jokowi's state speech demonstrate the government and his optimistic attitude toward coronavirus prevention, even though positive cases of COVID-19 increased during the delivery of the state speech. The launch of the COVID-19 vaccine campaign, which will begin in January 2021, or seven months before President Joko Widodo's state speech, reflects this hope.

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